

The Case for Connecting the Opens

A SPARC Europe Position Paper

Introduction and context

As digital transformation reshapes higher education (HE), outputs are increasingly being made accessible, shareable, and reusable through open approaches. These span data science, methods, publications, software, hardware, infrastructure, innovation, and education. Multiple forces drive the move towards openness in HE—improving accessibility, advancing pedagogy, meeting policy mandates, cutting costs, and responding to societal expectations.

However, open approaches in different areas of the work of HE have, until now, tended to be pursued in isolation. This position paper makes the case for ‘connecting the opens’ – a more co-ordinated approach that enables the exploitation of synergies and the maximisation of the benefits of openness.

The context

Open Access, Open Science and Open Education stem from the principle that knowledge should be a public good, freely shared and reused.

Open source and Open Access emerged in the 1990s. With open access, the research community sought to exploit the potential of the internet to enable the dissemination of research at low or no marginal cost. By providing free access to research publications, it aimed to overcome situations where only those institutions and individuals with the capacity to pay could access research. Many governments, funding agencies, international organisations such as UNESCO, and educational institutions now have open policies and legal frameworks that require the open access publication of publicly funded research.

Open Science evolved from the early sharing of publicly funded research in scientific societies. It now encompasses the application of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data principles, open methods, open infrastructure, open innovation, citizen science movements, and Open Access. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the power of open science, particularly in the context of connected open data. The rapid and transparent sharing of research data and findings significantly accelerated the development of diagnostic tools, treatments, and vaccines, ultimately benefiting society. More broadly, investment in OS has demonstrated returns on investment through increased innovation, job creation, and economic growth, as evidenced by the Human Genome Project and the development of GPS technology.

Open Education is rooted in traditions of accessible learning and has expanded through open universities, Open Educational Resources (OER) and openly licensed MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses). Governments are increasingly recognising the cost-effectiveness of open education in maximising the impact of public investments in higher education and supporting the development of quality curricula and learning materials in an era of increasing demand and tight resources. More generally, it has improved access to knowledge and online learning environments, demonstrably levelling the playing field for researchers and students who face mobility, financial, and lifestyle challenges, as well as fostering pedagogical innovations.

Today, digitalisation, evolutions in IP and publishing strategies, the development of tools such as Creative Commons licences, technological advancements such as AI, and a broader recognition of openness as a driver of innovation (both within the HE sector and beyond) set the stage for connecting OA, OS and OE. Although the UNESCO OS Recommendation connected these concepts in 2021, to date, few European countries have pursued national policies and strategies to connect Open Science and Open Education.

The value proposition

SPARC Europe believes that there is an opportunity to review policies and processes involving senior university leadership, faculty, libraries, IT services, and unions to 'connect the opens'. Rooted in open education and open-source traditions, the connected opens build inclusive, value-driven communities that encourage sharing, interdisciplinarity, and ethical scholarship, democratising knowledge. They transcend the silos of open initiatives, both within and across institutions, cultivating a network of shared learning and discovery. Open is a way of thinking, a mindset, and it is essential to harness its potential.

While recognising that each aspect of open offers distinct benefits, their more systematic integration facilitates the broader and more effective implementation of both open science and open education across the institution, for the reasons set out below.

Connecting the opens creates the conditions for the exploitation of synergies that **strengthen impact, equity, and efficiency**, resulting in a more robust and equitable higher education ecosystem. There is likely to be a particular gain for **Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion** (DEI) goals as HEIs can provide greater access to more diverse content that meets the needs of all, including traditionally underserved groups. There are also benefits for staff and student performance and satisfaction, as well as student future employability.

Increased access to research and educational output **makes learning more accessible to all**, at any time and from anywhere, thereby expanding access to higher education and lifelong learning for the workforce and non-traditional students. It thereby facilitates more growth and learning.

Following open source principles for research and education can also contribute to **improved safety, security, and privacy in digital learning environments** by allowing individuals and their institutions to take more control over their own content. It can also provide researchers, educators and learners with greater flexibility and freedom of choice in their tools and resources, thereby enabling a vibrant ecosystem of shared knowledge and collaborative development.

We can also expect to see more consistent **trust in HE** and its institutions through increased access to quality content, transparency, accountability, and collaboration with due regard for research security and AI needs and concerns. Greater transparency and increased inclusive collaboration allows for steps to address unethical conduct and to bolster the reliability of research and education.

Meanwhile, institutions can better **fulfil their civic responsibility** to the taxpayer by fostering collaboration in research and learning, making resources accessible, and preparing researchers and students as future bridge-builders. Integrating the opens is a powerful way to reshape this relationship, grounded in values of knowledge-sharing, collaboration, creating more equal opportunities, and collectively addressing societal challenges, such as those targeted by the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In addition, connecting the opens contributes to a more equitable and transparent academic ecosystem, reducing reliance on proprietary information services and systems, and promoting a different way of recognising and rewarding researchers, students and institutions. Through this, institutions can ensure **alignment with new local, national, and international assessment frameworks** such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), which promote the recognition of open works, including the creation and sharing of OER, in career progression.

Connected approaches are more likely to **catalyse innovation** and change in the sector. As digital transformation impacts the research and education system, cultures and mindsets will more easily change and realise the benefits of open practices when strategically addressed across the institution for research and education. Better co-ordination will also lead to more beneficial spillovers across diverse research and educational initiatives. Looking beyond synergies between different ‘opens’, there are also benefits from cooperation between institutions to drive approaches that place the needs of HE at the centre, not those of dominant publishers or big tech.

Finally, there are **economic advantages** to a more interconnected approach. HEIs face increasing costs for proprietary research and learning materials, services, and platforms, while also having to respond to demographic shifts leading to declining student enrollment. While the original motivations for open education may have been ideological, current adoption is increasingly driven by economic considerations, such as the need to use resources more efficiently. Furthermore, the desire to diminish the monopoly of large publishers for some and the need to adapt to changing government funding for HE are creating opportunities for open solutions. Outside of institutions themselves, governments will see the benefits of connecting the opens more strategically, in terms of faster innovation and stronger growth.

In short, interconnectedness improves knowledge reliability, accelerates problem-solving, reduces duplication, lowers costs, and supports more equity and fairness globally, while transforming the landscape of higher education and ensuring long-term institutional relevance and impact. Connecting the opens is not just a matter of efficiency or compliance; it is a fundamental step towards a more impactful, equitable, and future-oriented higher education system. Each institution, region and culture will take its own approach, responding to its own priorities and situation, but all stand to benefit from a connected approach.

Next steps

This SPARC Europe position paper launches a new European strategy to connect Open Science and Open Education, aiming to strengthen openness across European higher education and demonstrate the value of equitable access to knowledge. SPARC Europe aims to serve as a hub for universities eager to bring this concept to life.

We start by building an evidence base as we engage with university leaders around the concept. In the coming months, we will share more insights on the overarching vision and goals, as well as the drivers, barriers, policies, incentives, strategies, and resources supporting the implementation of connecting the opens, from the perspective of university leaders across Europe.

Acknowledgements

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SPARC Europe is here to support institutional leaders in championing an integrated open strategy. Going into 2026, SPARC Europe will connect experts and resources, convene communities of practice, and foster collaboration and capacity building for policymaking and strategy through events, knowledge exchange, and research.

Please follow our activities on Connecting the Opens here:

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